

IDEOGRAPHIC DICTIONARIES IN THE SYSTEM OF LEXICOGRAPHY

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Ideographic dictionaries are a specialized type of dictionary that focuses on the meanings and concepts associated with words rather than their phonetic or grammatical properties. They play a significant role in the field of lexicography, which is the art and science of compiling, writing, and editing dictionaries. Here's an overview of ideographic dictionaries and their place in lexicography:

Ideography is undoubtedly one of the main branches of modern lexicography. This is primarily due to the fact that the study of the structure of language and the linguistic landscape of the universe is carried out not only by philologists, but also by many scientific studies conducted by philosophers and psychologists. The ideographic dictionaries that are the subject of this science are still very popular today. This is especially true of English lexicography, which has existed since the early nineteenth century. It should be noted that despite the success of research in this area of Uzbek linguistics, it is much lower than in the field of original linguistics. The most striking examples of ideographic dictionaries in English are the first and most reprinted Roget's Thesaurus, Oxford Thesaurus, and Longman Essential Activators. In addition to the unique paper-based dictionaries above, it is worth mentioning active electronic dictionaries as well. One of the most successful dictionaries here is the WordNet dictionary, developed at Princeton University. It is also worth noting the achievements of local lexicographers who developed the ABBYY Lingvo dictionary. Because ideographic dictionaries have different appearances, they are divided into three types according to the traditional classification developed by V.V.Morkovkin:

1. Ideographic dictionaries. These dictionaries are divided into thematic groups. has a step-bystep hierarchical structure that reflects their interdependence. Each thematic group of such a dictionary has a key word that has a basic concept, as well as words that correspond to that concept. Such a view between vocabulary and word units is a visual tool that expresses the hierarchy of semantic connections. Using these dictionaries makes it much easier to locate and define specific words in the lexical-semantic system. The main disadvantage of the ideographic dictionary is that the lexical-semantic system of the word is given by the author of the dictionary, so the user may not always be able to find the word of interest in this dictionary.

2. Analogous dictionary. This type of ideographic dictionary is different in that the words in it are placed in the dictionary in alphabetical order. Each base word, as a rule, consists of small thematic groups consisting of words and phrases that are semantically compatible. Some analog dictionaries include word interpretations, lists of words with the same root, stable phrases, as well as information on extralinguistic features (e.g., in addition to the word "country" thematic group, there may be a table listing all countries in the world). Thus, analog dictionaries can combine ideographic, annotated, and even encyclopedic dictionaries. The advantage of analog dictionaries for users over ideographic dictionaries, in which the "fragmentary" presentation of the lexical-semantic system is presented in the form of a separate field, although the words are not specified separately.

3. Ideographic educational dictionaries. Such dictionaries are characterized by a large number of dictionaries created in many languages. As the name suggests, these dictionaries serve as auxiliary material in the study of foreign languages.

The volume of words in this dictionary is usually not large, rarely exceeding 10-12 thousand words. Words in a foreign language are divided into groups based on their relevance to the topic. This is why such dictionaries are sometimes referred to as thematic dictionaries. Along with each word, the language learner is given a translation into their own language.

Ideographic dictionaries serve several important functions that make them valuable resources for language learners, researchers, and anyone interested in understanding the nuances of meaning. Here are the main functions of ideographic dictionaries:

1. Meaning Exploration

- Understanding Concepts: They help users explore the meanings of words and phrases by grouping them according to their semantic relationships, allowing for a deeper understanding of concepts.

2. Vocabulary Expansion

- Learning New Words: By presenting related terms and synonyms, ideographic dictionaries encourage users to expand their vocabulary and discover new ways to express ideas.

3. Contextual Usage

- Real-Life Application: They often provide examples of how words are used in context, helping users understand appropriate usage and nuances in different situations.

4. Thematic Organization

- Focused Study: The thematic categorization allows users to study vocabulary related to specific topics or fields, making it easier to learn relevant terms for particular contexts.

The list of used literature:

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